

6. (a) E. C. FISHER and M. M. JOULLIE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1944; (b) *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**(i), 1649.
 7. S. K. GUHA, K. D. BANERJI and K. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 1011.
 8. D. J. RABIGER and M. M. JOULLIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 915.
 9. *Org. Synthesis*, Collective Volume IV, 1963, p. 569.

Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Copper(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl Acetophenonesemicarbazone

J. R. SHAH & R. P. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidhyanagar

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC studies on complex formation in iron(III)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone semicarbazone (5MeOAS) system have been reported earlier¹. The present communication describes the spectrophotometric study of green coloured complex formed by copper(II) and 5MeOAS.

Experimental and Results

5MeOAS was prepared as described earlier¹. Technical grade methanol was used after drying over anhydrous calcium chloride and then distilled. The stock solution of copper sulphate was prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of copper sulphate, the concentration of which was determined by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods.

Spectrophotometric measurements were made on Zeiss-spectol using 1 cm matched cells. All measurements were carried out at $30^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ in a 50% methanol—50% water (by volume) medium.

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper² was employed to determine the nature of complexes. Mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 mole-ratios of iron(III) to 5MeOAS were prepared. Absorbance measurements were carried out between 400 nm and 750 nm. The observations showed the presence of only one complex with $\lambda_{max} = 640$ nm formed in the system.

The composition of the complex was determined by three different methods, Job's³ using equimolar solutions, slope-ratio⁴ and mole-ratio⁵ methods. It was found to be 1 : 1 in all the three cases.

Effect of variation of pH on the degree of complex formation was studied. The optimum pH-range was observed to be 3.8 to 6.5 in which the complex was stable for several days.

The apparent stability constant, $\log K = 4.7 \pm 0.1$ of the complex was calculated from the absorbance data by the method of Mukherji and Dey.⁶

References

1. J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (in press).
2. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 427.
3. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
4. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
5. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1924, **16**, 111.
6. A. K. MUKHERJI and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314.

Synthesis of 5,7,8-Trimethoxy-3-methylchromone derivatives

Y. A. SHAIKH & K. N. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Baroda-2

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BENZO- γ -PYRONES or chromones having hydroxy or methoxy substituents in 5,7,8-positions are of interest as they are found in a great variety of compounds. Wiley¹ synthesised several chromones, which are found to have bronchodilator activity. We report here the synthesis of polymethoxy chromone derivatives, as this type of compounds, not only occur in nature but possess valuable therapeutic properties.

1,2,3,5-Tetramethoxy benzene², on Friedel-Crafts propionylation with propionic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride afforded 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy propiophenone³ (I), which when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acylation with acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate, yielded a product, which was insoluble in alkali. The I.R. spectrum of the product showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1660 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group). It has been assigned 5,7,8-trimethoxy-2,3-dimethylchromone⁴ structure (IIa).

I

II

a : R = -CH₃

b : R = -C₆H₅

Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation of compound(I), with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate afforded 5,7,8-trimethoxy-3-methylflavone(IIb). The I.R. Spectrum of (IIb) showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz., 1600 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl C = O group) and did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric-chloride solution.